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THE COMPARISON BETWEEN CLOUD COMPUTING AND GRID COMPUTING

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Abstract

It is a great idea to make many normal computers together to get a super computer, and this computer can do a lot of things. This is the concept of cloud computing. Cloud computing is an emerging model of business computing. And it is becoming a development trend. This article compares cloud computing and grid computing. Internet has connected all the computers in the world. Grid computing has been put forward under this background. Its core concept is to complete computing based on compute grid, in it every computer will devote power. In recent years a new concept cloud computing has been put forward, it can connect millions of computers to a super cloud. This article also introduces the application field the merit of cloud computing, such as, it do not need user's high level equipment, so it reduces the user's cost. It provides secure and dependable data storage center, so user needn't do the awful

things such storing data and killing virus, this kind of task can be done by professionals. It can realize data share through different equipments. The users need not know how the cloud runs. In this paper I describe the concept of cloud computing and grid computing and compare them.

Keywords: Cloud Computing, Grid computing; Distributed computer

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I. INTRODUCTION

What is the real meaning of cloud computing and grid computing? Everyone who engages in the IT world is talking about them. And a lot of people in the business world are asking this question, "What is cloud computing, and what does it mean for my business?"

Cloud computing platforms are growing very quickly. Let's explore the cloud computing infrastructure and its impact on critically important areas to IT, like security, infrastructure investments, business application development, and more.

Most IT departments are forced to spend a great deal of time and energy on its implementation, maintenance, and upgrade projects that too often don't add significant value to the company's bottom line. Increasingly, IT teams are turning to cloud computing technology to minimize the time spent on lower-value activities and allow IT to focus on strategic activities with greater impact on the business.

Grid computing is a network that is not in the same place but distributed resources such as computers, peripherals, switches, instruments, and data. Its resources may be owned by diverse organizations. Grid can be viewed as a special type of middleware that enable sharing and manage grid components based on user requirements and resource attributes.

You may have wondered about cloud computing as compared to grid computing. In this article, I talk about cloud computing service types and the similarities and differences between cloud

and grid computing. I discussed why cloud computing is more advantageous over grid

computing, what issues to consider in both, and some security concerns.

To make cloud computing work, what you need are three things: thin clients (or clients with a thick-thin switch), grid computing, and utility computing. Grid computing links separate computers to make a large infrastructure, use idle resources. Utility computing is paying for what you use on shared servers like you pay for a public utility (such as electricity, gas, and so on).

With grid computing, you can provide computing resources as a utility that can be used or not. Cloud computing moves forward one step further with on-demand resource provisioning. This eliminates over-provisioning when used with utility pricing. It also removes the need to over-provision in order to meet the demands of millions of users.

A user can get service from a full computer infrastructure through the Internet. This kind of service is called Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS). Internet-based services such as storage and databases are part of the IaaS. Other types of services on the Internet are Platform as a Service (PaaS) and Software as a Service (SaaS). PaaS offers full or partial application development that users can access, while SaaS provides a complete application, such as Enterprise Resource Management through the Internet.

To get an idea of how Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) is used in real life, consider The New York Times that processed terabytes of archival data using hundreds of Amazon's EC2 instances within 36 hours. If The New York Times had not used EC2, it would have taken it days or months to process the data.

The IaaS is divided into two kinds of usage: public and private. Amazon EC2 uses public server pools in the infrastructure cloud. A more private cloud service uses groups of public or private server pools from an internal corporate data center. You can use both types to develop software within the environment of the corporate data center, and, with EC2, temporarily extend resources at low cost—that is for testing purposes. The mix may provide a faster way of developing applications and services with shorter development and testing cycles. Cloud computing and grid computing are similar in many ways, what is the difference and relation between these two technologies?

II. THE BACKGROUND OF CLOUD COMPUTING

Nowadays, nearly everybody, every IT company is discussing the cloud. As is pointed in an article in *“Business Week”*, with the rapid development of cloud computing people can acquire software and computing power, this model will bring great changes to traditional IT business. It will become development trend. Though there is no precise definition about cloud computing, you can understand it in many ways. Originally, Cloud Computing was a unclear term for a very unclear and distant future in which computing would occur in a few remote locations without the need for very much human intervention. A great deal of computing resources would be available for any need at a low cost. Certainly, users would not need to know or care about how the computers, their software, or the network functioned. Without question it will affect every style in our work and life. With the rapid progress of the speed of internet and improvement of software of internet, cloud computing will solve more and more questions.

The first question you will ask is what is cloud computing. It is the development of distributed computing, parallel computing and grid computing, in other words it is the business realization of all these concepts.

The basic principle of cloud computing is to distribute the computing tasks to many distributed computers, not local computer or remote servers. This can make enterprise pay attention to the application, and visit computer and storage system according to its requirement.

Now we still use PC to do our work such as handles documents, store material, send Email or share files through U-disk. If our PC don't work, we will lose lots of data. But in cloud computing, cloud will do all these things for us. Cloud includes a lot of computers. Another advantage of cloud is the computers in it will be updated very often to keep the cloud active.

III. GRID COMPUTING

We must mention grid computing that is being used. Computing grids are conceptually not unlike electrical grids. In an electrical grid, wall outlets allow us to link to an infrastructure of resources that generate, distribute. And bill for electricity. When you connect to the electrical grid, you don't need to know where the power plant is or how the current gets to you. Grid computing uses middleware to coordinate disparate IT resources across a network, allowing them to function as a virtual whole. The goal of a computing grid, like that of the electrical grid, is to provide users with access to the resources they need, when they need them. Grids address two distinct but related goals: providing remote access to IT assets, and aggregating processing power. The most obvious resource included in a grid is a processor but grids also encompass sensors, data-

storage systems, applications, and other resources.

Many grids are appearing in the sciences, in fields such as chemistry, physics, and genetics, and cryptologists and mathematicians have also begun working with grid computing. Grid technology has the potential to significantly impact other areas of study with heavy computational requirements, such as urban planning. Another important area for the technology is animation, which requires massive amounts of disciplines. By making resources available to students, these communities are able to effectively model authentic disciplinary practices.

Grid provides a series of distributed computing resource through LAN or WAN. To the terminal user of application, as is he is using a super virtual computer. This idea will realize safe and coordinate resource sharing among person, organization and resources, and will create virtual and dynamic organization. Grid computing is a method of distributed computing. It includes location and organization, software and hardware to provide unlimited power. Its name is to make anyone in the grid can cooperate and access each other's information. But cloud computing is better; it has many advantages over grid computing in many ways.

Cloud computing evolves from grid computing and provides on-demand resource provisioning. Grid computing may or may not be in the cloud depending on what type of users who are using it. If the users are systems administrators and integrators, What they care is how things are maintained in the cloud. They upgrade, install, and virtualize servers and applications. If the users are consumers, they do not care how things are run in the system.

Grid computing requires the use of software that can divide and farm out pieces of a program as one large system image to a great number of computers. One concern about grid is that if one piece of the software on a node fails, other pieces of the software on other nodes may fail. This is alleviated if that component has a failover component on another node, but problems can still arise if components rely on other pieces of software to accomplish one or more grid computing tasks. Large system images and associated hardware to operate and maintain them can contribute to large capital and operating expenses.

IV. THE COMPARISON BETWEEN CLOUD COMPUTING AND GRID COMPUTING

First, we can compare those from job scheduling of grid computing. Job scheduling is the core value and aim of grid technology, its aim is to use all kinds of resources. It can divide a huge task into a lot of independent and no related sub tasks, and then let every node do the jobs. Even any node fails and doesn't return result, it doesn't matter; the whole process will not be affected. Even one node crashes, the task it should do will be reassigned to other nodes. Just like grid computing, cloud computing will make a huge resource pool through grouping all the resources. But the resources provided by cloud is to complete a special task. For example, a user may apply resource from the resource pool to deploy its application, not submit its task to grid and let grid complete it. From this point, the construction of grid is to complete a specified task, then there will be biology grid, geography grid, national educational grid and also. Cloud computing is designed to meet general application, and there are not grid for a special field.

Second, cloud will have effects in three aspects: the application in internet,

product application model and IT product development direction. Of course, this change is not subversion but some new characters that has been added. This advantage is a challenge to grid technology. When grid come it to being, it has some advantages, such as: you can provide unlimited compute power through any computer, and can get a great deal of information. This environment can help enterprise complete tasks that are very hard before, and use their systems efficiently, to meet the user's requirement and decrease the management cost. Cloud computing extends these advantages. More and more applications will be completed through internet by cloud computing. Cloud computing will extend the application of hardware and software, and will change the application model of hardware and software. Users can get an application environment or application itself not buying new servers and new software. To the users, the hardware or the software need not at his side or only used by himself, it can be available and virtual resources. And available resources are not limited inside the enterprise, it can be extended hardware and software attained through internet. The development direction of IT product will be changed to meet the above two conditions.

Cloud computing provides services in the following ways:

1) SAAS (Software as a service). This kind of cloud computing transfer programs to many users through web browser. In the user's eyes, he can save a lot of money in the servers and the authorization of software. In the supporters' eyes, he need maintain only one program, which will also save cost.

2) Utility Computing. This is an old idea. But it is produced in Amazon, IBM, Sun and other companies that provide

storage services and virtual servers in recent years. This cloud computing create virtual data center for IT business to collect memory, IO device, storage and computing power to make a huge virtual resources to serve the whole net.

3) Network service. It has close relation with SAAS, network service providers provide API to make developers develop more applications based on internet, not only the PC program.

4) Platform as a service. This kind of cloud computing provide a development environment. You can use middleman's device to develop your own program and deliver it to users through internet and servers.

5) Management Service Provider. It is one of the oldest application in cloud computing. This kind of application faces IT business not terminal users, it is often used virus scanning and program monitoring.

6) Business Service Platform. It is the mixture of SAAS and MSP. This kind of cloud computing provides a platform for the interaction between users and providers, such as personal budget management system, it can manage his budget and coordinate all the services he has booked according to the user's setup.

7) Integration of internet. It is to integrate all the companies that are doing the similar jobs. That will make it easier for the users to choose and select the service providers.

8) Infrastructure as a Service and more : A consumer can get service from a full computer infrastructure through the Internet. This type of service is called Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS). Internet-based services such as storage and databases are part of the IaaS. Other types of services on the Internet are Platform as a

Service (PaaS) and Software as a Service (SaaS). PaaS offers full or partial application development that users can access, while SaaS provides a complete turnkey application, such as

Enterprise Resource Management through the Internet.

To get an idea of how Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) is used in real life, consider The New York Times that processed terabytes of archival data using hundreds of Amazon's EC2 instances within 36 hours. If The New York Times had not used EC2, it would have taken it days or months to process the data.

The IaaS divides into two types of usage: public and private. Amazon EC2 uses public server pools in the infrastructure cloud. A more private cloud service uses groups of public or private server pools from an internal corporate data center. You can use both types to develop

software within the environment of the corporate data center, and, with EC2, temporarily extend resources at low cost—say for testing purposes. The mix may provide a faster way of developing applications and services with shorter development and testing cycles.

To grid computing, though its resources have been pooled, it looks like a huge resource pool from outside. But to the user who has submitted a special task, he doesn't know which node will complete his job. What he need do is to submit his job to the grid according to a special style, and then what he will do next is waiting for the result. And the grid job schedule system will look for the resource that is matched to job, and find idle physical node, send out the job until the job will be finished. Though grid can realize parallel job processing, the user has to prepare the algorithm himself, and send them to

different physical nodes. This process is a little complicated, that is why many grid computing are built to complete special requirements. Cloud computing will cut the physical resource through virtual method. From this point it can realize allocate resource according to the need and increase automatically. This kind of increase can't exceed the up limit of the physical nodes. Though from the view of control point, cloud will look all the IT resources as a resource pool, different physical node will be divided in different resource pool. That is the difference between grid computing and cloud computing in the allocation of resource.

From the concept, cloud computing is actually a kind of distributed computing; this computing model has advantages and huge potential over the computer model in traditional database. At the same time, some experts has pointed out that automation technology is the base of any cloud computing infrastructure. Automation technology is also the base of any advanced computing technology. If you want to use cloud computing in any case, it means you have no reusable process, and it also means you are trying to let others do the job that you are not sure to do.

V. CONCLUSION

Though cloud computing has many advantages over grid computing, clouds will not replace grids, as grids have not replaced capability HPC, over the last 10 years, as some have predicted. All three technologies have their place, What we will see over the next couple of years is that these different computing nodes will more and more grow together with the World Wide Web and the Internet, until all these resources become one global infrastructure for information, knowledge, computation and communication, the World Wide Grid.

We think it is more likely that grids will be re-branded or merge into cloud computing, Grid computing helped create a certain technology reality which made clouds possible. And when it comes to IaaS [infrastructure as a service], I think in five years something like 80 to 90 percent of the computation we are doing could be cloud-based.

In a word, the concept of cloud computing is becoming more and more popular. Now cloud computing is in the beginning stage. All kinds of companies are providing all kinds of cloud computing service, from software application to net storage and mail filter. We believe cloud computing will become main technology in our information life. Cloud has owned all the conditions. Now the dream of grid computing will be realized by cloud computing. It will be a great event in the IT history.

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